

eDNAqua-Plan

NEXT GENERATION OF AQUATIC BIODIVERSITY MONITORING

Operational input from all use cases
on existing workflows and tools to be
used in WP3

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Summary

Milestone 9 gathers feedback from freshwater and marine use cases to the tasks embedded in Work Package 3. Challenges faced by scientists when using and creating taxonomic reference databases, when submitting high throughput sequencing data to public repositories or DNA-based occurrence data to biodiversity portals are documented and translated into a set of recommendations that should be considered by WP3 when creating the digital ecosystem for DNA-based aquatic datasets.

A primary issue for the reference databases is the need for automated pipelines with built-in quality controls to improve quality, transparency and reproducibility of taxonomic data produced by environmental DNA (eDNA) studies. Additionally, a framework for genome skim data from reference specimens and biobanks is needed, and inconsistencies in taxonomic assignments for prokaryote datasets need to be tackled. Moreover, Metagenome Assembled Genomes (MAGs) are used as a reference for taxonomic and functional annotation of metagenomic prokaryotic datasets, but clear criteria for taxonomic assignment of the MAGs are often lacking.

In terms of sequence data repositories, raw sequencing reads from several marine and freshwater test cases are submitted to general repositories, which are not searchable and hence not recommended for use. European projects also rarely upload their data to the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA), which is linked to the fact that data submission to ENA requires more knowhow and is less intuitive than submitting to its US-American counterpart, i.e. NCBI Sequence Read Archive (SRA). To ensure the long-term usability of DNA-based datasets and the reproducibility of derived results, robust data management plans, but also additional guidelines and practical support on how to provide required metadata into repositories are needed. The use cases further demonstrate that species occurrence datasets are rarely uploaded to public biodiversity repositories, despite the increase in eDNA and bulk DNA research. This generates a substantial gap in accessibility of the newly generated biodiversity data using DNA-based methods.

Interoperability between repositories presents further challenges. Scientists generating eDNA and bulk DNA datasets typically use the scientific papers as the primary point of data exchange. This is problematic since the data flow is not searchable when only links in a publication are provided. In addition, data submission often bypasses essential data processing steps, resulting in outdated or incomplete links in the repositories. Clearer guidelines are needed to specify where and how biodiversity data, especially from marine and freshwater environments, should be submitted. This needs to include also the way how DNA based biodiversity databases are interlinked with classical morpho-taxonomic biodiversity data and how taxonomic backbone information is harmonised across repositories.

The digital ecosystem for DNA-based biodiversity analyses of the future needs to address these issues to greatly improve the transparency, accessibility, and usability of DNA-based datasets for biodiversity research and monitoring.

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Abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation/Acronym	Definition
BIOPOLIS	Associação Biopolis
DMP	Data Management Plan
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic acid
eDNA	Environmental DNA
EMBL	European Molecular Biology Laboratory
EMBRC-ERIC	European Marine Biological Resource Centre - European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ENA	European Nucleotide Archive
EU	European Union
EV ILVO	Eigen Vermogen Van Het Instituut Voor Landbouw - En Visserijonderzoek
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
GA	General Assembly
GBIF	Global Biodiversity Information Facility
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GSC	Genomics Standards Consortium
IAB	International Advisory Board
IHU	Diethens Panepistimio Ellados
INRAE	Institut National de Recherche pour l'Agriculture, l'Alimentation et l'Environnement
LifeWatch-ERIC	E-Science European Infrastructure for Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research - European Research Infrastructure Consortium
MAG	Metagenome Assembled Genome
MDA	Marine Data Archive
NIVA	Norsk Institutt for Vannforskning
OBIS	Ocean Biodiversity Information System
SSBE	Seascape Belgium
SRA	Sequence Read Archive of the National Center for Biotechnology Information
SU	Sorbonne Université
SYKE	Finnish Environment Institute
TDWG	Biodiversity Information Standards
UDE	Universität Duisburg-Essen
ULOD	Uniwersytet Lodzki
UMINHO	Universidade do Minho
UNESCO	United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization
UVEG	Universitat de Valencia
VLIZ	Vlaams Instituut Voor de Zee
WP	Work Package
WU	Wageningen University

1. Introduction

The current digital ecosystem for submitting eDNA and bulk DNA-based sequencing reads consists of various options at national and international level. Repositories can be selected that are specifically designed for sequencing data (e.g. European Nucleotide Archive ENA, Sequence read archive SRA) or are more general systems to deposit data (e.g. Zenodo, FigShare, Dryad). The advantage of more specific repositories is that entries are not only findable and accessible, but also searchable. Despite the large amount of sequencing data generated for aquatic environments and the massive amount of funding accompanying this sequencing effort, there is currently no streamlined approach on where aquatic DNA-based datasets should be submitted to and which metadata they should minimally contain to allow reuse of the data. Furthermore, DNA-based datasets provide a large amount of species occurrence data once sequencing reads have been processed. Incorporating DNA-based occurrence data in general biodiversity repositories, such as GBIF or OBIS, would greatly enhance our knowledge on species distributions in aquatic environments. Further, linking the taxonomic data to environmental metadata would help to shed light on the ecology of the studied taxa and responses to pressures. Similar to raw sequencing data, it is important that information on how the sequences were processed is available to the community for reproducibility of results. Of particular importance in this respect are reference databases that are used to assign taxonomic names to sequence data. Various such reference databases that contain sequences with taxonomic names obtained from vouchered specimens or biobanks exist. Likewise, bioinformatic pipelines to add taxonomic names to newly obtained sequencing data using these reference databases exist. However, the level of quality control and curation among reference databases differs substantially. The diversity of different databases, differences in their strategies to data quality as well as differences in software for taxonomic assignment illustrates the need for proper metadata governance and reproducible workflows.

The aim of WP4 is to gather the experience of a diverse audience that is actively generating real-world eDNA and bulk DNA datasets from aquatic environments. Based on this audience WP4 aims to get insight into the used strategies for sharing generated sequence data and the metadata accompanying the sequence data. The use cases tackle different target taxa (fish, invertebrates, unicellular eukaryotes and prokaryotes), use different sequencing strategies (metabarcoding, mitogenomics, metagenomics) and operate in freshwater and marine environments. As such, they provide valuable information on the current state of data submission and on the hurdles and difficulties that users are facing with the current digital ecosystem.

2. Strategy of WP4 to provide operational input to WP3

WP3 aims to design a digital ecosystem for DNA datasets that is fully in line with the FAIR principles, especially consisting of interoperable modules, not only with-based databases, but also on those based on classical morpho-taxonomy and the associated environmental metadata. WP4 provides operational input to all three tasks of WP3 to ensure that the digital landscape of the future is practical and straightforward for the users that are actually generating the data. To achieve this, the focus is on best practice recommendations to obtain reliable reference records from genetic databases (T3.1), on aligning metadata across DNA sequence repositories (T3.2) and on improving links between different infrastructures to increase dataflow and connectivity between different data systems (T3.3). A template excel was prepared to structure the information for the 22 use cases (see milestone 8 for detailed information on the use cases) into the following main topics:

- Metadata fields required by the repository to which raw sequencing reads are submitted with example of how metadata fields were filled by use cases; this allows to see commonalities in metadata across repositories and provides a direct overview of typically provided data
- Metadata fields required by the repository to which processed sequencing reads are submitted with example of how the metadata fields were filled in by the use cases; this allows to pinpoint metadata fields that are shared with repositories for raw sequence read submission and for which duplication of effort can be avoided

- Information on reference database used and curation steps (if) taken; this provides input on how use cases are assigning taxonomy to processed sequencing reads
- Explanation of the taxonomic assignment method, including the used thresholds

A summary of the information provided by the use cases is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Summary of the information provided by the use cases. For each use case, the monitoring program or project, the geographic sampling area, the target group, the environment, sample type and data type are listed. If the data has been submitted, then the repository for raw and processed sequencing reads is listed. The reference database used to assign taxonomy and the availability of the bioinformatic pipeline to assign taxonomy are also listed. "Info lacking" indicates that for certain use cases, the partner institute was not able to provide the requested information by the milestone deadline.

Use Case #	Monitoring program/Project	Geographic region	Target group	Environment	Sample type	Datatype	Repository raw reads	Repository processed reads	Reference database used	Pipeline to assign taxonomy
ILVO_1	GEANS - sand extraction pilot	Belgian part of the North Sea	macrobenthos	marine	bulk DNA	metabarcoding short read	SRA	not submitted	GEANS v4.0	available
ILVO_2	GEANS - offshore windfarm pilot	Belgian part of the North Sea	fish	marine	eDNA seawater	metabarcoding short read	SRA	GBIF	own refseq + Genbank nt	available
ILVO_3	GEANS - offshore windfarm pilot	Belgian part of the North Sea	invertebrates	marine	eDNA seawater	metabarcoding short read	SRA	GBIF	GEANS v4.0 + BOLD + MIDORI (no insects)	available
INRAE_1	WFD monitoring program/OFB project/Aquaref project/Synaqua	France, mainland, overseas departments	epilithic diatoms (microbenthos)	freshwater	bulk DNA	metabarcoding short read	Recherche Data Govv	Recherche Data Govv	Diat.barcode v9	available
WUR_1	RVO tender new offshore wind	Dutch part of the North Sea	fish	marine	eDNA seawater	metabarcoding short read	MDA	MDA	Genbank nt	info lacking
WUR_2	RVO tender new offshore wind	Dutch part of the North Sea	metazoa	marine	eDNA sediment	metabarcoding short read	MDA	MDA	Genbank nt	info lacking
UVEG_1	ClimaWet	Mediterranean wetlands	bacteria-archaea	freshwater	water and sediment	metabarcoding short read	SRA	not submitted	SILVA 138.1 database	available
UVEG_2	Ecolake	Mediterranean wetlands	bacteria-archaea	freshwater	water and sediment	metabarcoding short read	SRA	not submitted	SILVA 134 database	available
UVEG_3	Wetlands4Life	Iberian wetlands	bacteria-archaea	freshwater	water and sediment	metabarcoding short read	SRA	not submitted	SILVA 138 database	available
UVEG_4	Karstic Lakes Project	Mediterranean continental lakes	bacteria-archaea	freshwater	water and sediment	metagenomics	SRA	not submitted	non-redundant rdp 16/18S database	available
UVEG_5	Quality network network	Iberian wetlands	macroinvertebrates	freshwater	Sediment	metabarcoding short read	not submitted	not submitted	BOLD/Genbank	not available
UVEG_6	Mediterranean DCM project	Mediterranean Sea	bacteria-archaea	marine	seawater	metagenomics	SRA	not submitted	non-redundant rdp 16/18S database	available
UDE_1	GeDNA (governmental monitoring)	German streams	invertebrates	freshwater	bulk DNA	metabarcoding short read	ENA	not submitted	BOLD	available
UDE_2	GeDNA (governmental monitoring)	German streams	diatoms	freshwater	bulk DNA	metabarcoding short read	ENA	not submitted	diat.barcode database v11.1	available
UDE_3	JDS4 (Joint Danube Survey)	Danube sites	invertebrates	freshwater	bulk DNA	metabarcoding short read	ENA	not submitted	BOLD	available
UNESCO_1	eDNA expeditions	Worldwide (World Heritage Marine Programme MPAs)	metazoa	marine	eDNA seawater	metabarcoding short read	SRA	not submitted	own refseq from Genbank nt	available
UNESCO_2	Pacific Islands Marine Biodiversity Alert Network (PacMAN)	Suva harbour, Fiji	invertebrates + unicellular eukaryotes	marine	bulk DNA + eDNA	metabarcoding short read	SRA	first part of data submitted to OBIS	MIDORI, Genbank nt	available
UMinho_1	NIS-DNA	Portuguese coast	invertebrates	marine	bulk DNA + eDNA	metabarcoding short read	SRA	not submitted	BOLD and SILVA	available
BIOPOLIS_1	Long-term ecological research project	Iberian rivers	fish	freshwater	tissue	mitogenomics	SRA	Bankit (annotated genomes) + BOLD (COI and Cytb)	BOLD + Genbank nt	available
BIOPOLIS_2	Long-term ecological research project	Portuguese rivers	fish	freshwater	eDNA water	metabarcoding short read	not submitted	not submitted	own refseq + Genbank nt	available
SYKE_1	GeMeKa	Baltic sea	prokaryotes + unicellular eukaryotes	marine	eDNA seawater	metabarcoding short read	info lacking	info lacking	info lacking	info lacking
SYKE_2	TIMED	Finnish lakes	invertebrates	freshwater	bulk DNA	metabarcoding short read	not submitted	not submitted	BOLD	available

3. Operational input from the use cases to T3.1

T3.1 aims to assess the required information and validation criteria for reference records in genetic databases so that these can be either directly used for reliable taxonomic assignment or that curated, highly reliable genetic reference databases can be extracted from these public databases. The marine use cases have used “quality controlled” reference databases to assign taxonomy to macrobenthos and invertebrates (GEANS, BOLD, MIDORI), while fish and prokaryotes are assigned using either custom made reference libraries or using the nucleotide database of NCBI. For the freshwater use cases, invertebrates and diatoms are assigned taxonomy using databases that are curated (Diat.barcode V9) or have quality control options (BOLD), while prokaryotes, in this case, are assigned using the SILVA database, though the use of NCBI is not uncommon for this type of data. Fish taxonomy assignment was performed using the nucleotide database of NCBI and BOLD.

Points of consideration for T3.1:

1/ Reference databases should be created using automated pipelines with imbedded quality control of the sequences to increase transparency and repeatability across eDNA studies

Taxonomic information is added to metabarcoding sequencing reads by comparing them with reference sequences from public reference collections. Most case studies rely on reference databases (BOLD, MIDORI; table 1) which apply a quality control system when new sequences are added thereby ensuring that the taxonomy is trustworthy. However, when non-standard marker genes are used (e.g., 18S for metazoas) or when metagenomic datasets are generated, the nucleotide sequence collection of NCBI is used. Taxonomic verification of the sequences in NCBI is absent which may lead to incorrect species names in the eDNA dataset. Also, the quality control of BOLD still allows several erroneous sequences, or sequences with taxonomic names assigned via “reverse BIN taxonomy” (Weigand et al. 2019). Although BOLD flags dubious records during initial submission of the reference data, these flags are not taken into consideration when metabarcoding reads are being compared to BOLD.

Case study ILVO_2 was used to compare taxonomic assignments of eDNA fish data using a manually created 12S reference database without taxonomic verification with an automatically generated database with taxonomic verification. Both databases were created using a species list of 120 marine fishes caught in the area since 1978. The manual reference database contained reference sequences from the ILVO barcode reference collection and from NCBI (one 12S sequence was chosen per species, geographically closest to the BPNS; no phylogenetic inference was performed to check the species name). This reference database contained 118 sequences (maximum of 1 sequence per species). The species list was also used to create an automated reference database using the meta-fish-lib script (Collins et al. 2021). The script includes phylogenetic inferences to remove unreliable sequences that may come from wrongly identified specimens. The automated reference database contained 240 sequences (multiple sequences per species were kept). Taxonomic assignment of the eDNA reads were conducted using RDP embedded in Dada2 (bootstrap 80). Both databases detected 56 species, of which 53 were shared. However, in terms of ASVs, the automated pipeline was able to assign more ASVs to species level (78.5 % of all fish ASVs compared to 62.6 % for the manual reference database). Furthermore, the automated pipeline ensures highly transparent and repeatable database construction and allows for easy updates. We therefore recommend using such automated pipelines for assigning taxonomy to eDNA datasets. It is also recommended that the parameters to generate the species lists used in such automated pipelines to extract sequences from public databases are well documented, so that this list can be recreated. For EV ILVO, it became clear that the parameters used to create the species list of fishes for the Belgian part of the North Sea had not been documented properly, which made it impossible to recreate the exact same species list. Since the species list is the basis for populating the reference database used for taxonomic annotation with reference sequences, it is important to also sufficiently document this step.

Case study UDE_1 was used to compare the composition of invertebrate communities found in 170 German stream samples, inferred by morphology and DNA metabarcoding and to compare associated

inferences of the ecological status class required by the EU Water Framework Directive (2000/60/EC). A short standard marker (COI, primers fwHf2, fwHr2n, Vamos et al. 2017) was used for metabarcoding, data were processed with APSCALE (Buchner et al. 2022) and taxonomic assignment was made by comparing OTUs against BOLD using the pipeline BOLDigger (Buchner and Leese 2020). BOLDigger flags taxonomic names returned from the reference database BOLD depending on issues such as an assignment with ambiguous hits, a single hit only, a hit to only a non-public (private) entry or a hit against an entry without morphological identification (reverse BIN taxonomy). The use case assigned 1006 invertebrate species compared to 439 species detected by morphology. 303 species were shared between approaches (Macher et al. 2024). The study found several cases of database errors in BOLD due to either misidentification or other errors, which still persist in the database.

2/ Harmonisation of taxonomic names between repositories is needed to maximise comparability of species detected across different studies

Case study UDE_1 also revealed several taxonomic errors in species names or synonyms when comparing the assigned taxonomic names to the GBIF taxonomy. The use case proposed a curated and versioned (DOI) list of invertebrate species with quality controlled (including e.g. phylogenetic placement) sequence data to be compiled for regulatory biomonitoring to maximise comparability and reproducibility of results. Such an approach is used by some use cases already (e.g. ILVO - GEANS reference database). The results of UDE_1 also highlight the need to harmonise taxonomic names between repositories (e.g. GBIF, nationally used taxonomic system, Catalogue of Life, BOLD, NCBI and e.g. the Freshwater Animal Database (FADA) used in FIP).

3/ A framework for genome skim reference data from vouchered reference specimens is needed

Although the current effort for DNA reference databases is focused on single locus marker genes, the continuous advances in sequencing technology have shown that genome skim data from vouchered specimens can be used to create reference mitogenomes (Margaryan et al. 2020) and reference databases of unassembled reads to identify samples (Bohmann et al. 2020). The advantage of genome skims from vouchered specimens is that all existing DNA barcodes (mitochondrial and nuclear) can be generated in one go. Use case BIOPOLIS_1 is an example of this, where full mitogenome sequences of freshwater fish have been created. Raw sequencing reads were submitted in NCBI SRA, while the annotated full mitogenomes were published through NCBI BankIt. This use case experienced submission of the raw sequencing reads to ENA as less user-friendly compared to the submission process to NCBI SRA. Taxonomic verification of the assembled mitogenomes was done by extracting COI and Cytochrome *b* genes and querying them against the BOLD and NCBI databases (%id>99%), respectively. Additionally, phylogenetic tree analyses were performed to confirm phylogenetic relationships between species, which included full mitogenomes of Iberian freshwater species publicly available in NCBI GenBank. COI gene sequences were deposited in BOLD. Data was published in the form of a data paper, where links to data and metadata in NCBI and BOLD were made and also provided in FigShare. Guidelines on how to make genome skim data compliant to the FAIR principles are needed.

4/ Automated taxonomic assignment of prokaryote metabarcoding datasets by sequence repositories is inconsistent with taxonomic assignments reported in the scientific publication

For metabarcoding of prokaryotes, the NCBI SRA accepts raw sequencing data directly from high-throughput sequencing platforms. As these datasets are inherently large and sensitive to contamination, a common procedure is to deposit the raw sequences without processing. The processing of the sequences and taxonomic assignment is usually associated with a publication after the time of submission. However, SRA submissions are processed by the repository itself and a taxonomic assignment to each of the deposited samples is made available for download along with the raw sequences.

The process of taxonomic assignment by NCBI is done at the level of reads by means of “k-mer-based Sequence Taxonomic Analysis Tool (STAT)”. Based on MinHash, and inspired by Mash, STAT employs

a reference k-mer database built from available sequenced organisms to allow mapping of query reads to the NCBI taxonomic hierarchy (Katz et al. 2021). This preliminary step is justified by the premise that submissions must be processed, before either interpretation or quality assessment is possible, to provide submitter feedback and submission verification. This implies that all submitted sequences have an associated taxonomy. Subsequent taxonomic assignments published in the corresponding articles do not necessarily coincide completely with those made by NCBI (as illustrated by use case UVEG_1), thus producing a duplicity that, as a general rule, is not resolved in a subsequent verification process.

5/ Metagenome Assembled genomes (MAGs) from prokaryotes are used as reference for taxonomic and functional annotation of metagenomic datasets but often lack clear mentioning of the criteria used to assign taxonomy

Metagenomics approach, in addition to submitting raw sequences, allows the construction of MAGs (metagenome-assembled genomes) which can then serve as a reference for recruitment of reads to infer taxonomy and potential functionality of microbial taxa. Along with the raw metagenomic reads, all available MAGs (assembly) for that metagenome can be submitted. The taxonomic assignment of each MAG is performed with The Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB), an initiative to establish a standardised microbial taxonomy based on genome phylogeny using the software GTDB-Tk toolkit. The correct taxonomic assignment is essential for the deposited genomes to serve as a reference. The criteria used by GTDB itself to select genomes from NCBI and be included in the GTDB reference trees and database is based in (1) CheckM completeness estimate >50%, (2) CheckM contamination estimate <10%, (3) quality score, defined as completeness- 5*contamination, >50 (4) contain >40% of the bac120 or arc53 marker genes, (5) contain <1000 contigs, (6) have an N50 >5kb and (7) contain <100,000 ambiguous bases. This information is not mandatory in the process of MAG submission and is critical for the possible use of MAGs as a reference for recruitment of reads to infer taxonomy and functionality of microbial taxa.

4. Operational input from the use cases to T3.2

T3.2 aims to align metadata standards for sample collection, experimental methods, sequencing and bioinformatic analyses across the repositories.

Repositories used to submit marine raw sequencing datasets were either the sequencing read archive of NCBI (SRA, 7 use cases) or the Marine Data Archive (MDA, 2 use cases) which is a general data repository to store marine datasets. Freshwater datasets were submitted to SRA (5 use cases), the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA, 3 use cases) or to a general national data repository (Recherche Data Gouv, 1 use case). Importantly, four freshwater use cases have not submitted the raw sequencing reads to any repository at this point (Table 1).

Repositories for processed sequence reads (i.e. sequence data that have been bioinformatically transferred into a species occurrence or abundance table) have been rarely used. Of the 22 use cases, only one freshwater and five marine use cases have submitted their processed sequencing reads to public repositories. These repositories were either a dedicated biodiversity platform (GBIF, OBIS) or a general platform for data storage (MDA, Recherche Data Gouv). The freshwater dataset entails the assembled mitogenome data for which the annotated full mitogenome was submitted to Bankit and the barcode loci COI and Cytb were submitted to BOLD.

Points of consideration for T3.2:

1/ Submission of sequencing reads to general repositories should be avoided

To comply with the FAIR principles, existing repositories specifically created for sequencing data (ENA, SRA) should be used compared to general repositories (Zenodo, FigShare, dryad, MDA, Recherche Data Gouv) that do not offer a comparably metadata-rich and interoperable environment.

2/ Submission of sequencing reads from European projects are rarely deposited in the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) but this should be the recommended platform

Only three use cases have submitted their data to ENA, and reported that the ENA guidelines should explain more thoroughly on how the different data structures are connected. A more "compact" guideline would be useful to improve the data submission process. ENA is considered the more suitable option for European projects because of self-applied data protection regulations aligned with the EU-General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), but also because of established contacts with EMBL-EBI (which hosts ENA) in several European Biodiversity projects. Furthermore, we consider the probability of negative consequences due to governmental shutdowns less likely for a European intergovernmental institution compared to a US-hosted governmental institution.

3/ The use of existing metadata standard templates needs to be encouraged for upload of sequencing data to public repositories

Several templates with standardised metadata information on genomic or metabarcoding studies have been proposed, e.g. by the Genomics Standards Consortium (GSC, <http://www.genesc.org/pages/projects/mixs-gsc-project.html>) with the MxS template (suitable for any DNA data) and MIMARKS template (suitable for marker gene data from the environment or from specimens) being particularly relevant for DNA-based raw sequencing datasets. SRA provides these templates during upload of the raw sequencing data and additional columns can be added to the template to list negative control information or marker gene information. Only half of the use cases that submitted to SRA (six out of the 12) used the MIMARKS survey template. The other six studies used NCBI specific templates. The three use cases that submitted their data to ENA reported that they were not able to use such a standard metadata checklist. Based on this, a more streamlined approach across the sequencing repositories and clear guidance towards the use of these standard checklists is needed to create a digital ecosystem of DNA-based data.

4/ A proper data management plan needs to be in place to ensure the second-life of DNA-based datasets

It is detrimental to have a good data management plan already from the start of a project, and to adhere to this DMP throughout the project execution and beyond. This is illustrated by SYKE_1, where raw sequencing data had accidentally been saved on the CSC (National IT Center for Science in Finland) server, in a so-called scratch folder, where large amounts of data can be stored, but which is regularly cleaned by CSC. The commercial sequencing company still had the raw data, which was surprising considering that there was a two-year gap between the sequencing and this exercise. This example highlights the importance of submitting molecular data to proper data repositories right after a project is finalised.

5/ DNA-based biodiversity datasets are seldomly uploaded to public repositories which forms an important gap in the current digital ecosystem

Processed sequence reads that list species occurrences or abundances have only rarely been submitted to repositories (GBIF, MDA, Recherche Data Gouv) for the use cases at hand. OBIS, the Ocean Biodiversity Information System, has been used by only one marine use case, while this should be the primary dataflow for marine datasets. The same holds true for the Freshwater Information Platform (FIP), which focuses on classical taxon occurrences. Thus, despite the huge number of biodiversity studies being conducted using eDNA or bulk DNA, such datasets do not yet find their way to the biodiversity portals. Clearly, this is an important gap in the current digital ecosystem that needs to be tackled. GBIF with the eDNA toolkit offers the uptake of eDNA data (Nilsson et al. 2022) and has been tested by two marine use cases (ILVO_2 and ILVO_3). Despite a fairly easy and user-friendly submission process, the workflow seems to not be well established in the use cases.

5. Operational input from the use cases to T3.3

Task 3.3 will map the different infrastructures used in aquatic biodiversity monitoring workflows with the aim to improve the links between these infrastructures and services. Of the 22 use cases, only three (ILVO_2, ILVO_3 and UNESCO_2) have submitted the processed sequencing reads to a biodiversity portal. The two case studies from ILVO were used to look at the provenance of the data of sample collection all the way to submission of the species occurrence data into GBIF.

Points of considerations for T3.3:

1/ A scientific paper cannot be the central point of data sharing in the digital ecosystem

The two use cases entail eDNA metabarcoding data from fish and invertebrates in the Belgian part of the North Sea which have been published in a scientific open access paper (Cornelis et al. 2024). The metadata of sample collection, lab processing and bioinformatic processing are listed in the data access statement of the scientific paper, which contains the links to the raw sequencing data in SRA, to the processed data in GBIF and to the bioinformatic scripts used to process the raw sequencing reads in Zenodo and Github. Assuming that this use case is representative for the workflow of the scientific community, the scientific paper is the central point of data sharing: the material and methods section of the paper outlines how the data was collected and processed and the necessary links are provided to the data files. However, this does not create a digital ecosystem containing searchable data provenance. This was illustrated when the data provenance of the ILVO use cases was traced back starting from the GBIF records. For instance, finding DNA-based datasets in GBIF in general, and the ILVO eDNA dataset in particular, using the search tool available in GBIF was challenging. In addition, fields are available to list the bioinformatics protocol or the lab protocol, but these are not mandatory. Since this information was provided in the paper, these fields were left blank in GBIF thereby compromising the access to this information. Data fields with links to the raw sequencing reads in SRA were completed, although also this information was not mandatory in GBIF. Regardless of which fields should be mandatory or not, the digital ecosystem should ensure that upload of metadata is standardised across the various repositories, so that the effort required to provide the data is minimised. For example, if the same data fields need to be filled in, then at least the template files should be streamlined as much as possible between the repositories to avoid duplication of effort. Standard ontologies for metadata fields should be used (e.g. recommendations by Biodiversity Information Standards (TDWG) and GSC).

2/ Data submission to repositories does not follow data processing steps leading to outdated or incomplete links across repositories

Data publication from a project is not conducted in the same order as data processing. For instance, many journals require that the raw sequencing data have been submitted to sequence repositories before the scientific publication can be accepted for publication. This means that the link to the scientific publication needs to be added to the sequencing (and biodiversity) repositories in a later stage. Once the publication is accepted, there is no reminder that this information needs to be updated in the different repositories. The same holds for adding links to the raw sequencing reads in GBIF: the species occurrence data can be uploaded without providing the links to the raw sequencing data files. The digital landscape should therefore foresee automated reminders to the data submitters to ensure that the updated URLs are provided in due time.

3/ Clear guidelines on where to submit biodiversity data for marine and freshwater datasets are needed

At this point, there are two marine biodiversity platforms (OBIS and EMODnet) and one global biodiversity portal (GBIF). The GBIF portal has an option to send the marine data to OBIS. During the general assembly meeting, the advisory board highlighted that specific attention for correct data flows of marine and freshwater datasets need to be set to allow proper data tracking. For freshwater biodiversity, the freshwater information platform (FIP) and the associated freshwater biodiversity data portal are linked with GBIF ("The Freshwater Network" in GBIF). So far, no eDNA data have been

submitted through these data portals. Clear guidelines linking to proposed solutions (e.g. Nilsson et al. 2022) should be considered as a key deliverable to improve this.

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